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Trust Development in Isolated, Confined, and Extreme Teams

Report

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Trust is one of the most important aspects of successful human collaboration, especially in isolated, confined, and extreme (ICE) environments, like polar stations and expeditions. The more people we have working together, the more complex both the task-related and social interpersonal relationships become - trust being the glue keeping those teams intact.

“Yes, trust is the fundamental element. It's an isolated and extreme environment and for my own safety, trust is the most important thing. I would not do all this work if I would not trust people I work with and of course there are new people coming in, and every expedition I get people who I don't know and or I haven't known a long time. We have these rules and regulations and agreements. So, I first of all... I have to trust that people are following this. I have to trust that these people are such people I can communicate with and we can find solutions”

- an Antarctic station commander.

This report is the outcome of a two-study research project. In the following pages, we describe the practical recommendations from the project and its methods.

If you are interested in the more technical nuances of the study, reach out to andres.kaosaar@ucf.edu.

Practical recommendations

The main question the report provides insight on is: **how can we achieve high performance in an ICE team?** Since the research project focuses on trust, we take a trust-centered lens.

First, in this project, we discuss three main trust-related variables: cognition-based trust, affect-based trust, and psychological safety.

- **Cognition-based trust** develops when a person believes that a team member (or the team) is knowledgeable and skilled enough to do what is needed.
- **Affect-based trust** is based on an emotional bond and belief that the team members (or the team) have your best interests at heart.
- **Psychological safety** describes the state where individuals feel comfortable being themselves, taking interpersonal risks, and expressing their thoughts and feelings without fear or negative consequences.

For working on improving trust in a team, the first step should always be figuring out what is the problem you are trying to solve. What are the specific symptoms of reduced/low performance and how are they tied to specific behaviors and attitudes in the team?

At the same time, it's important not to forget the parts of the team that work well - what are the aspects that we want not to change?

This is important since, depending on the aspect we are trying to develop, we need to choose the specific trust-related dimension to work on but we cannot forget the other aspects. For example, our findings indicate that cognition-based trust is more related to general safety and team effectiveness, and cohesion compared to affect-based trust and psychological safety. At the same time, affective trust is paramount for psychological well-being and social climate, and is strongly connected to teamwork quality while psychological safety is related to teamwork quality and social climate as well.

Moreover, we have to ensure that we won't damage other aspects while working on a specific trust-related variable. If we start working on cognitive trust to enhance general safety but in doing so forget to ensure that affective trust and psychological safety won't get damaged in that process, we might accidentally influence teamwork quality, social climate, and psychological safety in ways that were not intended.

The following table illustrates which aspects of trust the team could focus on to support specific outcomes.

Desired outcome/ trust dimension	Cognitive trust	Affective trust	Psychological safety
General safety	✓		
Teamwork Quality	✓	✓	✓
Teamwork effectiveness	✓		
Team cohesion	✓		
Social climate		✓	✓
Psychological well-being		✓	

The next question is: **how to enhance cognitive trust, affective trust, and/or psychological safety in the team?**

The three trust-related dimensions are strongly based on four types of perceptions regarding the team: the abilities of the team, the benevolence of the team members, the integrity of the team members, and the level of identification with those team members.

In the following table, it is shown which of those aspects significantly influence which of the trust-related dimensions.

	Cognitive trust	Affective trust	Psychological safety
Ability	✓		
Benevolence		✓	
Integrity	✓	✓	✓
Identification	✓	✓	✓

Depending on our identified problem and focal trust dimension, the next question is, **how can we enhance the ability, benevolence, integrity, and/or identification in the team?**

This answer has two sides - first, the perceptions of the team members regarding their team. Meaning, that maybe the team has the required level of ability, benevolence, and integrity, but the team members are just not aware of that, i.e., don't perceive the team like that. In that case, interventions that would familiarize the team members with each other's characteristics and the shared capabilities of the team itself would be recommended. This includes different team-bonding and -building exercises that include both social aspects (for developing perceptions of integrity, benevolence, and identification) and collaborative problem-solving/task-based aspects (for developing ability). For some recommendations, see the Additional Resources section below.

The second side of the answer is the actual capabilities of the team and team members. This part has two sides as well - the emergent capabilities of the team members as a dynamic mechanism stemming from the collaboration and coordination between the individuals and their capabilities, and the knowledge, skills, abilities, and other characteristics (KSAOs) of the individuals.

So it is important to determine if the problem you are trying to solve comes from teamwork issues and the lack of successfully integrating the KSAOs of the individuals or are some of the individuals lacking the necessary skills for being a functioning part of the team (i.e., is it a teamwork or taskwork issue). Depending on this, the next step would be either to train the teamwork of the team, focusing on effective and clear communication, coordination, and collaboration (teamwork), or to work on the skills and abilities of the team members (taskwork).

On the other hand, the necessary KSAOs of team members also cover personality or other traits that are not so easily trained. This means that the issue at hand can also stem from a simple incompatibility between team members' personality constellations or team members' unfitness for the role and/or environment. In this case, it would be recommended to think about finding a better-fitting role for the person and/or replacing the person from the team with someone more suitable.

Additional resources

Lencioni, P. M. (2002). *The Five Dysfunctions of a Team: A Leadership Fable*. John Wiley & Sons.

Salas, E., Shuffler, M. L., Thayer, A. L., Bedwell, W. L., & Lazzara, E. H. (2015). Understanding and improving teamwork in organizations: A scientifically based practical guide. *Human resource management, 54*(4), 599-622. <https://doi.org/10.1002/hrm.21628>

Sample

Study 1

Interviews about trust development in Antarctica (N = 9)

39.5

Average age

1 Estonian

8 Finnish

Study 2

A two-wave quantitative survey on trust antecedents, trust dimensions, and trust outcomes (N = 136). Data was gathered in the summer (Northern Hemisphere) of 2023.

Men

Other Women

38

Average age

Average team size

Average mission length

Mission season

Mission region and stations/vessels (70 unique), "other" containing stations/vessels with less than 2%

Participant nationalities, "other" containing nationalities with less than 3%

Research team

Andres Käosaar, MA

Andres Käosaar is a Doctoral Student in the Industrial-Organizational Psychology program and a Graduate Research Assistant at the University of Central Florida. He holds a BA and MA in Psychology from the University of Tartu, Estonia, EU.

His research focuses on team dynamics in Isolated, Confined, and Extreme (ICE) environments, with the main interest in astronaut and polar teams. He is currently involved in projects related to interpersonal relationships, trust, resilience, cultural diversity, affective states, and regulation, and team cognition on team dynamics and performance in teams operating in space, space simulation missions, and Antarctic stations.

In 2023 he was awarded the Early Graduate Student Researcher Award by the American Psychology Association's Science Student Council.

Moses Rivera, MSc

Moses is a doctoral candidate in the Industrial-Organizational Psychology Ph.D. program at the University of Central Florida.

His research focuses on enhancing various outcomes for teams of cross-disciplinary knowledge workers and high-level decision-makers, and helping workers become ready for teamwork. His recent work has focused on psychological safety as a key antecedent of high performance in teams.

His dissertation investigates the role of work passion in teams, and how it may impact psychological safety.

Pedro Marques-Quinteiro, PhD

Pedro Marques-Quinteiro is an organizational psychologist, with a passion for developing human performance in extreme environments. With over a decade of experience providing training and consultancy to business companies, fire departments, and polar research groups, he currently works as an Associate Professor at Universidade Lusófona.

He is involved in research projects supported by the Portuguese Polar Program, the Portuguese Space Agency, and the European Space Agency.

He has led two scientific expeditions to King George Island (Antarctica) to study teamwork in extreme environments.

C. Shawn Burke, PhD

C. Shawn Burke is a Research Professor and Director of the TRACE lab at the Institute for Simulation and Training, University of Central Florida. Her expertise includes teams and their leadership, team adaptability, team training, measurement, evaluation, and team effectiveness.

Dr. Burke has published over 90 journal articles and book chapters related to the above topics and has presented/had work accepted at over 200 peer-reviewed conferences.

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